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**A STUDY OF CORRELATION AMONG EMOTIONAL BEHAVIOUR,
COMMUNICATION SKILL AND ADJUSTMENT OF STUDENTS
ON THE BASE OF SEX DIFFERENCE**

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Abstract

This study was carried out on 640 students between 12-16 years age group of Senior Secondary school of Ajmer district is done for the study of correlation among Emotional behavior, Communication skill and Adjustment of students on the base of Male & Female, is revealed for the sample of the purpose of random method. Emotional Behaviour Scale, Communication Skill Scale (created By Scholar) and Adjustment Scale, are used as tools for data collection. T-test and coefficient test of correlation, statistics method are used for the Analysis of collected data's. A difference is noticed in Emotional Behaviour, Communication Skill and Adjustment of Male and Female school students at the same time, a difference is studied in the relation of Emotional Behaviour and communication skill.

Introduction:

Education can only be significant when it can mould a man in such a way that he can choose peace as his life style and an have a power to solve any problem that he can not only be an idle spectator. It has capacity to keep the nation, healthy and energetic with the peaceful

attitude in which curriculum of school is harmonised but 12-18 year is teen age that is a stage of Emotional development of young pupils, if they are not paid attention their life in future is effected. Emotion is internal feeling So the experience of Emotions is found different from other. IZARD has presented a group of ten basic Emotions like- JOY, SURPRIZE, ANGER, AVAMANG, FEAR, SHAME, CRIME, INTEREST AND EXCITEMENT, these connectivity produce different kinds of Emotions.

Volter (1974), there are eight basic Emotions all other Emotions are the conscience of the mixture of same basic Emotions. He has revealed these Emotions in for contrary couples like - joy, sorrow, willing, unwilling, fear, anger and wonder pre-realisation. The experience of Emotional Behaviour depends on the sequence of the activation of physical sense. The assumption of Emotion is by their verbal and nonverbal expressions. These verbal and non-verbal expressions do the work of communication source. A man becomes able to understand. The feelings and expressions of himself and others.

The higher volume of speaking levels peach like specialities and accent of the words are included in the medium of pronunciation of Communication Skill. These other non-verbal characteristic of language and timely characteristic are called overcome language, facial expressions, dynamic (physical position and body language) and nearest (physical distance in face of face interaction) Behaviour are included in other non-verbal mediums. The most famous medium of Emotional Behaviour is blandishment of face Communication of mouth place of very important in a daily life most other people are successful in balancing of Emotions. They try to adjust with them and follow defense mechanism of progressive work to face. These Adjustment solution protect them from different Emotional Behaviour like anxiety, weariness etc. Anxiety is that state which a man develops in his failure of self resepect.

We often face douatful circumstances in our life, fear anxeity, unwillingness like negotional emotions are developed in any man during difficult and stress condition. If these types of negotional Emotions are continuously allowed for long time, they may have negative effect on physical health and psychology of man, this is the reason that most of the functions of stress management considered the management of the Emotions is necessary for stress management. The focus of Emotional management depends on decrease in negotional Emtionas and increase of Negotional. Successful Emotinal Management is the key of Effective Social Adjustment.

According to Mehlla, S.K. (2008) has considered Emotional Development as a very important factor of Educational Growth and Development in every activity of man, his Emotional Behaviour is revealed effect physical, social, mental and learning process as well as his areas of Adjustment. According to Scott, T. & Joseph, P. (2010). The students are correlated with various Communication Skills and Emotions in school environment. According to Nishida (1985) cultural Adjustment, Communication Skill and language, all are correlated. Logan, Sarah, Nughes, N. (2011) told that cognitive factor communication depends on Internal Inspiration and intelligence of the students like- reading, writing and speaking, these are correlated with the internal relation of the students. According to Khan, M.A. (1976) Adjustment effects the man in Emotional, Creativity and sensitivity. Kumari, S. (1982) told that the level of Adjustment is effected by many factors in Sociometric Groups like- Social Status, Family Status, Emotional Behaviour and Educational Environment.

Above Mentioned Research studies revealed that the relation of Emotional Behaviour, Communication Skill and Adjustment these three variable are not studied together. Thus Researchers have tried to study the correlation of above variables.

Emotional Behaviour :

Baran, Byrne and Kantowitz (1980), by Emotion we mean a subjective feeling state involving psychological arousal, accompanied by characteristic behaviours. Sanstrok (2000), We will define Emotion as feeling or effect, that can involve psychological arousal, conscious, experience and Behavioural expression. Emotional Element of man is connected with the extrovert expression in which divert communication, body language physical posture, volume, ideas are some such elements that revealed Emotional Behaviour of a man. these are effected by learning, culture and the Environment of the school. In this present study Emotional Behaviour means- students of adequate depth of feeling, adequate expression and control of Emotions, ability to function with emotions, ability to cope with problem. Emotions, enhancement of positive Emotions.

Communication Skill: Communication :

is called heart of education because not only education but also teacher and common Behaviour can't be imagined without communication. Communication is a process to

communicate, ideas, attitude, sensitivity, logics and exchanged of knowledge between two or more than two persons. So communication works to maintain human and Social Environment. Singh (2005) Explained that the working behaviour of all living and non-living exist in nature are directly or indirectly dominated by communication as language is developed, the various methods of communication, as completion in communication, clarity, unity, effects are also developed. In the present study communication skill is used, in language writing, language speaking language listening, body language.

Adjustment:

According to Boring, Longfield & Weld 'Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence, the satisfaction of these needs. According to above definition there is balance of Adjustment and the Adjustment is arranged in the atmosphere which is constituted with complicated aspects of natural, Emotional, Biological, Social, Cultural and Educational. The standard opinion of Dr.S.K. Thakur explained that if biological and psychological demands of any man are self satisfied than life will be very easy and comfortable but there are several hindrance. Regarding individual environmental problems prevent satisfaction. So these obstructs create difficulty to adjust Emotional, Social and Educational. Problems in present study, the meaning of Adjustment is the adjustment of aspects.

In present study, the Adjustment of correlation Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skill of Male & Female students of school is tried to explain.

Objectives of the study:

- ❖ To find out the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skills of Male and Female School students.
- ❖ To find out the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment Skills of Male and Female School students.
- ❖ To find out the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Communication Skills and Adjustment of Male and Female School students.

Hypothesis of the study:

- ❖ There will be no significant difference between the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Emotional behaviour and Communication Skill of Male and Female schools students.
- ❖ There will be no significant difference between the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Emotional behaviour and Adjustment Skill of Male and Female schools students.
- ❖ There will be no significant difference between the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Communication Skill and Adjustment of Male and Female schools students.

Method of the study :

Survey method of research was used in this present study.

Sample for the study:

This study was carried out on 640 students from 12-16 year age group of senior secondary school studying Male and Female students of Ajmer District is done for the study of sample selection by purpose of Random Method.

Tool used for the study :

1. **Emotional Behaviour scale** - standarised by Dr. Harish Sharma and Dr. Rajivlochan Bhandari.
2. **Communication Skill Scale** - Developed by Investigator Dr. Rakesh Katara and Dhruva Kumar Mittal.
3. **Adjustment Inventory** - Standarised by prof. A.K.P. Sinha and Prof. R.P. Singh.

Statistical Techniques used In Study :

The obtained datas were analyzed using 't' test and coefficient test of correlation.

Analysis and Interpretation of the data :

Statistical Analysis of Male and Female schools students (n=640) about Emotional Behaviour, Communication Skill and Adjustment are measured in data`s and shown in following tables :

Table No. - 1
Coefficient of Correlation and 't'- values between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skills of Male and Female school students.

First Variable → Second Variable ↓	Emotional Behaviour		
	Male school students	Female school students	't'- value
Communication Skill	-0.051	0.082	1.667

Significant level of Correlation on the level of 0.05 - .113 on the level of 0.01 - .148
 Significant level of 't' value on the level of 0.05 – 1.96 on the level of 0.01 - 2.54

It is observed from above table no. 1 that correlation -0.051 is acquired between the Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skill in the group of Male School students. It is negative correlation and no significant value on the level 0.05. On the other hand, in Female school students, this correlation 0.082 is acquired in the group of female students ,it is no significant on the level 0.05.

The 't' value 1.667 is the acquired, Coefficient of correlation of Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skill in the Male and Female school students. This is Less than 1.96 Significant value of significant level 0.05. Hence we can conclude that there is no effect of sex difference on the coefficient of correlation between above mentioned both variables.Because of it , There will be no significant difference between the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Emotional behaviour and Communication Skill of Male & Female schools students , H_{01} is first selected.

Table No. -2
Coefficient of Correlation and 't'- values between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment of Male and Female school students.

First Variable → Second Variable ↓	Emotional Behaviour		
	Male school students	Female school students	't'- value
Adjustment	-0.360	- 0.042	-4.029

It is observed from above table no. 2 that correlation -0.360 is acquired between the Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment in the group of Male School students. It is negative correlation and significant value on the level 0.01. On the other hand, in Female school students, this correlation -0.042 is acquired in the group of female students it is negative correlation and no significant on the level 0.05.

The 't' value -4.029 is the acquired, Coefficient of Correlation of Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment in Male and Female school students. This is more than 2.54 Significant value of significant level 0.01. Hence we can conclude that, there is effect of sex difference on the coefficient of correlation between above mentioned both variables., There will be no significant difference between the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Emotional behaviour and Adjustment Skill of Male & Female schools students H_{O_2} is second rejected.

Table No. -3
Coefficient of Correlation and 't'- values between Communication Skill and Adjustment of Male and Female school students.

First Variable → Second Variable ↓	Communication Skill		
	Male school students	Female school students	't'- value
Adjustment	-0.024	0.058	1.036

It is observed from above table no. 3 that correlation -0.024 is acquired between the Communication Skill and Adjustment in the group of Male School students. It is negative

correlation and no significant, value on the level 0.05. On the other hand, in Female School students, this correlation 0.058 is acquired in the group of female students, it is no significant on the level 0.05.

The 't' value 1.036 is the acquired Coefficient of Correlation of Communication Skill and Adjustment Correlation in Male and Female school students. This is Less than 1.96 Significant value of significant level 0.05. Hence we can conclude that, there is no effect of sex difference on the coefficient of correlation between above mentioned both variables. Because of it There will be no significant difference between the effect of Sex Difference on correlation between Communication Skill and Adjustment of Male & Female schools students H_{O3} is third selected.

Conclusion :

1. There is no significant correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skills of the male school students.
2. There is no significant correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skills of the female school students .
3. There is no significant difference in the scores of correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skill between male and female school students.
4. There is significant correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment of the male school students.
5. There is no significant correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment of the male school students.
6. There is significant difference in the scores of correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment between male and female school students . Consiquently a difference is found between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment of the student of the male and female school students.
7. There is no significant correlation between Communication Skill and Adjustment of the male school students.
8. There is no significant correlation between Communication Skill and Adjustment of the female school students.
9. There is no significant difference in the scores of correlation between Communication Skill and Adjustment between male and female school students.

Educational Implication :

It is observed from the conclusion study that there is no direct significant correlation between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skill of the male and female school students but the difference of correlation is significant between Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skill of the both students on the other side no significant correlation is found between Emotional Behaviour and Adjustment of the female students, but this correlation is negative and significant in the male students and difference is significant between the correlation of the students of both sex. So the educationist should identify those factors which create difference between correlation of Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skills of the students due to the sex difference. Those factor should also be identified that create the difference between correlation of Emotional Behaviour and Communication Skills of the students on the base of sex difference of study. Also announces that laps of Emotional Behaviour effects the adjustment of the students negatively. So the female school students should be trained for Emotional Behaviour Management so that their Adjustment may be strong, stage play, Games competition, debate and creative efforts of presentation can direct the positive. Emotional Behaviour of the students, this Emotional Behaviour can be helpful in the Communication Skills of the students after transformation.

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